

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: CARTWRIGHT-JOHNSON****FIRST NAME: SHAWN****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE (1)****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did not use Zotero (had issues)

The author used Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 7)

List your six key concepts with the page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Preparatory steps in essay writing (EUCLID 2024, 6-9)
2. Achieving logic flow in writing EUCLID 2024, 39)
3. American and British English EUCLID 2024, 24-32)
4. Punctuation (EUCLID 2024,15-23)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 33-39)
6. Style Guide (EUCLID 2024,41-42)

SIX IMPORTANT CONCEPTS IN ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Writing an academic paper can be intimidating as it requires, among other things, significant research, the establishment of a question, the creation of a coherent structure and clear writing to address the question, critical thinking, a balance of ideas, and an exhibition of scholarship.

The ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack period one (1) is an invaluable reference exploring critical points in drafting academic papers, providing samples and examples. Eight chapters offered a comprehensive coverage of the essay writing process. It provided an overview of how to get started in academic writing – researching and finding a question to address in research. It then introduced fundamental writing skills, such as the basic structure of the essay, including the introduction, body, and conclusion, and provided the content of these parts. It later discussed paragraph structure, punctuation, transitional words, phrases, and more advanced concepts of style and writing requirements of Euclid.

It addressed the critical concepts of referencing and plagiarism, which, according to EUCLID (2024, 34), are severe academic offenses with numerous significant consequences. It provided practical methods to avoid plagiarism, such as using proper citations and quotation marks. It provided tools such as Chicago Style crib sheets, Latin abbreviations and their meaning, eight pages of general rules on punctuation, and references in text suggestions for websites such as BBC Style Guide for the readers to explore to illustrate style.

It further provided a model answer for a similar response paper, which has helped identify errors in my essay and some of the pitfalls to avoid.

This paper will explore only six key points that resonated most with me. First, I begin with steps in essay writing, then move on to achieving logical flow. After these two topics, it will sequentially explore American and British English, punctuation, plagiarism, and style guides.

2) STEPS IN ESSAY WRITING

It is essential to read widely, read articles and books on the area of research with the idea of taking notes and looking at potential targets to write about. Reading can help you fine-tune the question or topic of your writing. One key point stated by EUCLID 2024 made early was "never procrastinate" (EUCLID 2024,7). This advice is essential as deadlines for completing assignments or writings are critical to motivation and part of professional responsibility, necessary for being a prolific writer.

Note-taking while reading helps organize your thoughts and write plans. The reader can use ideas from his notes to populate the structure, which should include an introduction, body, and conclusion (EUCLID 2024,10). Successful academic writers must adhere to the rules of writing, which require using paragraphs that contain coherent and logically developed arguments. The main idea in each paragraph should be clear and follow logically with appropriate transitions (EUCLID 2024, 12).

3) ACHIEVING LOGICAL FLOW

At the end of Chapter 4 on plagiarism, EUCLID (2024, 39), the concept of "logical flow" was introduced. According to the writers, logical flow happens when using headings, transitional phrases, and words. It helps the reader to have a smooth and logical flow from one idea to another. If done correctly, this would allow a logical flow of the arguments and ideas in the essay. A few examples of these words and phrases are: In addition, further, previously, and finally. EUCLID (2024, 39) has included "despite this," "as a result," and "nevertheless," among a few other examples. These words make the paper coherent and are as important as keeping the paper consistent in using one form of English.

4) AMERICAN AND BRITISH ENGLISH

This section of the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack for period one was the most illuminating. Before reading this chapter, I was confident that British English would be my choice for this paper for two reasons:

1. I was a citizen of a former British territory, The Bahamas, and
2. My formative schooling made sure I spelled the British way

The latter led me to the knowledge that there were differences in spelling and pronunciation, but I was unaware of many differences in usage and punctuation.

However, on studying the differences in usage with large collective nouns, pluralized adjectives, the same word but different or additional meanings, general syntax, use of periods, commas, and quotation marks, and so on, I then realized that I was indeed in the camp of American English. This realization gave me greater faith in "the seven points" of why US English is currently the dominant influence on world English. The "magnitude of US mass media" and "American popular culture" have tremendously influenced our written and spoken language (EUCLID 2024, 25).

5) PUNCTUATION

Another area of focus for EUCLID 2024 was punctuation. They spent nine pages covering commas, dashes, and semi-colons. Punctuation is vital to writing, as the whole idea of writing is to convey ideas to others. Punctuation makes the difference. A critical part of punctuation was that of quotations. According to (EUCLID 2024, 23), a writer should use quotations to capture direct speech in writing or words or statements from other writers.

In the latter case, EUCLID (2024, 35) discussed the use of quotations for long and short quotes, illustrating how to use them to avoid plagiarism.

They stated that the quotation marks should bracket the actual words spoken like this: "...". Further, they said that should the lifted statement be four or more lines, be necessary, then it would be best to put the lines in an indented paragraph so that they stand out.

The use of quotation marks is also necessary for the prevention of plagiarism. The chapter also explained using other punctuation, such as dashes and the colon.

6) PLAGIARISM

EUCLID 2024 has defined plagiarism as the situation "when a writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information" (EUCLID

2024, 34). In addition to being unethical, plagiarism is also “a serious academic offence.” (EUCLID 2024, 34).

To avoid plagiarism, the use of citations, either in-text or long quotes with quotation marks, is suggested by EUCLID (2024, 34). In-text citation embeds the quoted words and name of the author and page into the writer’s paragraph, while the latter can be brief or extended for more than four lines and may be created by an indented stand-alone paragraph. In this latter case, there are no quotations. (EUCLID 2024, 35).

The chapter advises not to use quotations extensively but rather use them when the author has used strong language that emphasizes the meaning and is persuasive for the argument being made (EUCLID 2024, 36).

To avoid plagiarism, the use of footnotes and a list of Works cited can also be useful tools to help illustrate the source of materials used in academic papers.

7) STYLE GUIDES

A fourteen-page Chicago Style Euclid guide was provided in the ACA-401 ACA-401D course pack 1. I also viewed the YouTube video by Dr. Gulma, Informative, and watched the review of a paper and the application of the proper EUCLID style guide in real-time.

The style guide, according to EUCLID (2024, 41), “provides a means of documenting basic rules or features of your writing that will allow you to ensure consistency in your written output.”

According to EUCLID (2024, 41), a style guide includes manuscript layout, accepted terminology, readership considerations, structure, paragraph numbering, and indentation, to name a few.

This chapter on style guides advocated a look at the BBC News Style Guide as a concrete example of a style guide. It was found at (bbc.co.uk/newsstyleguide), and it stated, “Audiences expect the BBC to demonstrate the highest standards of English because well written stories are easier to understand.... Although it is only a guide for journalists, it details many of the rules of spelling, punctuation, and grammar. It also covers accuracy, fairness, and impartiality. The Oxford dictionary is the otherwise the preferred reference.”

In an example used, the term “Mankind” was critiqued by the BBC Style Guide as “open to objections of sexism -safer to write the human race, people etc.”

8) CONCLUSION

The ACA-401 ACA-401D course pack for period one, written by Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, has been a source of foundational knowledge and inspiration.

As I studied each section, I discovered so much information that I have already improved as a writer. I found out that my English is American, so when should I use the n-dash? Stop procrastinating and write!

It has reinforced the rules of grammar and writing essays. Still, the program has added other aspects to my research arsenal, such as using Grammarly, Zotero, and parts of MS Word I have never explored.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.